

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND NUTRITIONAL VALUE OF WHEAT, BARLEY AND CORN GRAINS

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Annotation: The purpose of the work is to study the chemical composition and nutritional value of wheat, barley and corn grains before and after preparation for feeding (by flattening, germination, extrusion and complex germination and extrusion). The research objectives are to determine the chemical composition and nutritional value of wheat, barley and corn depending on the methods of preparation for feeding.

Key words: The purpose, chemical composition, nutritional value, barley and corn grains, flattening, germination, extrusion and complex germination and extrusion, chemical composition, barley and corn depending.

INTRODUCTION

When developing new and improving well-known technologies for processing feed grain, it is necessary to pay attention to increasing the nutritional value of the resulting product at an optimal level of increasing labor and energy costs for preparing feed and maintaining its minimum cost. When studying mechanical methods of grain processing before feeding, the above conditions and the effect of prepared feed on the productivity of animals were taken into account. From the literature, such methods as processing grain with heat, moisture and mechanical action are known [1-10]. It is appropriate here to characterize the methods of preparing grain for feeding (flattening, germination and extrusion) studied by us, to reflect the positive and negative sides of these methods. All of them are aimed at increasing the availability of grain nutrients to the digestive system of animals and thereby increasing their digestibility and digestibility. Flattening destroys the hard shell of the grain well, and its action is directed only from the physical side, without changing the nutrients of the raw materials. Germination acts on the transformation of the nutritional properties of grain more effectively than flattening. In sprouted grain, the concentration of starch, sucrose, fat and nitrogen-free extractives decreases. In this regard, there are fewer feed units and exchange energy in grain with sprouts and roots compared to their content in natural grain without processing. At the same time,

germination has a positive effect on the concentration of raw and digestible protein, fiber, the sum of sugars, glucose+fructose, carotene, vitamins B1, B2, C and E [2-4]. There is evidence that when corn seeds germinate, the activity of free phytohormones increases [6]. However, the method of germination of grain, in addition to the above-mentioned positive qualities, has disadvantages. Sprouted grain is not stored, it must be immediately fed or dried on high-temperature aggregates.

But in the process of prolonged exposure to high temperature on raw materials, some vitamins are lost, which reduces the quality of the feed product. A method of grain extrusion before feeding to animals is also known. With it, the processed raw materials undergo profound changes in the structure of nutrients at the cellular level and their transition into a more digestible form. These changes in the feed occur as a result of a sharp drop in pressure when the heated grain mass exits the extruder, which entails an "explosion" (increase in volume) of the product, making it more accessible to the enzymes of the gastric tract of animals, thereby improving the quality of the processed feed. Therefore, extrusion should be preferred in terms of a more effective effect on feed, compared with other methods [5, 7]. We propose to combine two rational methods (germination and extrusion) into a complex sequential process of preparing grain for feeding. First, the grain is germinated, and then extruded. Next, the finished extrudate is crushed and packed or mixed with other components of the feed mixture or compound feed. The purpose of the work is to study the chemical composition and nutritional value of wheat, barley and corn grains before and after preparation for feeding (by flattening, germination, extrusion and complex germination and extrusion). The research objectives are to determine the chemical composition and nutritional value of wheat, barley and corn depending on the methods of preparation for feeding.

OBJECTS AND METHODS

Germination of wheat, barley and corn was carried out in the conditions of the feed mill as follows. First, the grain was soaked for one day, and then the swollen grain with a humidity of 40-45% was spread out in ridges with a height of 30-40 cm (in the first one day) and 15-30 cm (in the next 1-2 days) to obtain sprouts and roots with a length of 1.0-1.5 cm. In the formed ridges under the temperature was kept at 10-15oC, but not higher than 18-20oC. To reduce the temperature, the ridges were stirred every 2-3 hours. In the same room where grain germination was carried out, an extruder of the PE-KMZ-2U brand was installed. Wheat, barley and corn grains were extruded on it at a

temperature of 130-140°C and a pressure of 2-3 MPa. At the same time, the residence time of the feedstock in the unit was 8-13 s. The chemical composition of wheat, barley and corn grains was studied with the determination of: humidity — after convection drying of samples to a constant mass at a temperature of 102-105°C; total nitrogen — according to Kjeldahl; crude fat by the difference before and after extraction in the Soxhlet apparatus according to the method of S.V. Rushkovsky; crude fiber — by the method of sequential processing of the suspension with sulfuric acid, alkali, alcohol and ether according to Genneberg and Shtoman; ash — by burning the suspension in a muffle furnace to a constant mass; calcium — by the titrimetric method; phosphorus — by the calorimetric method using phosphor-molybdenum-vanadium acid; total sugar and starch content — with the use of an antron reagent; carotene — according to E.A. Nesterova; vitamins A and E — according to the VISH method.

THE EXPERIMENTAL PART.

Results and discussion Natural wheat grain was subjected to various processing methods before feeding in order to identify the most effective in terms of a positive effect on the chemical composition of the processed product and increase its nutritional value. For this purpose, the following methods of grain processing were used: flattening, germination, extrusion and extrusion of sprouted grain. If the first three methods (flattening, germination and extrusion) are known, then the latter method, which includes two processes (germination of grain and its subsequent extrusion), is new. The chemical composition and nutritional value of wheat grain, depending on the method of its processing before feeding, are presented in the table. It follows from the data in the table that the methods of processing wheat grain before feeding affect its nutritional value and chemical composition. At the same time, the calculation of nutrients in the processed grain was carried out per 1 kg of dry matter. Therefore, all types of preparation of wheat grain for feeding were put in the same conditions and it is better to compare and analyze changes in feed under the influence of any factor on dry matter than on the initial humidity. Comparing the applied methods of processing wheat grain, we can conclude that the complex method deserves attention. First, the grain must be germinated, and then extruded. This allows, in comparison with natural grain without processing, to increase the EKE, crude protein and crude fiber in the feed, respectively, by 0.8, 19.0 and 18.2%. At the same time, double processing of wheat grain (first germination, and then extrusion) significantly increased the

amount of total sugar, calcium, phosphorus, vitamins A and E in the extrudate, respectively, by 5.89 times; by 60.0 and 37.1%, as well as by 2.2 and 4.82 times. However, some nutrients in the finished extrudate decreased compared to natural grain without processing. Thus, the content of crude fat has decreased by 18.5%, BEV — by 5.6 and starch — by 25.5%.

CONCLUSION

Thus, it can be noted that the complex preparation of wheat, barley and corn grains for feeding (first its germination, and then extrusion) has a positive effect on the chemical composition, contributing to an increase in the finished extrudate for all types of the above-mentioned grain of crude protein, total sugar, calcium and phosphorus, respectively, by 6.2-27.9%;

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